

L3 Harris Response to JPL's Open Source Science for NASA Earth System Observation Mission Science Data Processing Study Request for Information

Company Background

L3Harris Technologies is an agile global aerospace and defense technology innovator, delivering end-to-end solutions that meet customers' mission-critical needs. The company provides advanced defense and commercial technologies across space, air, land, sea and cyber domains. L3Harris has approximately \$18 billion in annual revenue and 47,000 employees, with customers in more than 100 countries. This business includes developing the ABI sensors on the GOES East and West satellites and the ground operation system. L3Harris Geospatial Solutions, Inc (HGSI) is a subsidiary to L3Harris Corporation. It sits within the Space & Airborne Systems group. HGSI develops commercial off the shelf software products (ENVI/IDL/Jagwire), services for geospatial image analytics and has provided software for government programs of record for analysing, cataloguing and distributing scientific data. L3 Harris is committed to a diverse and inclusive work environment, products include VPAT statements, one of our key goals with HGSI COTS software is democratizing access to complex data and analysis.

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1 Data processing System Architecture

L3Harris has developed a unique high performance data processing system capable of running arbitrary science algorithms on very large, real time data streams. It has been in operations for over six years on the GOES-R mission, producing 200,000+ diverse weather products (over 2TB) per day per satellite with 99.5% availability. The system is based on running a tuneable number of instances of an algorithm with the data stored in a distributed shared memory cache of tenable size. The processing throughput can be increased and latency lowered by increasing the number of instances of an algorithm and increasing the number of cache servers. See Figure 1 below. Our system has been ported to a cost effective, cloud native implementation that offers very high scalability with no built in limits. We have demonstrated processing a 600Mbps data stream from a simulated hyperspectral sounder in real time. We believe our system is ready to scale now to processing petabytes of data per day through its tuneable parallelism combined with the scalable computing resources available in the cloud.

Figure 1, GOES processing chain to delivery NRT products from vast amounts of imagery

Via the HGSI team, Jagwire, a commercial off shelf application capable of cataloging, storing, disseminating and visualizing EO/IR, SAR, LIDAR, SAR, Thermal data and interacting with vector data via ESRI products or other GIS tools is available to support NASA’s open data initiatives. Data stored in the Jagwire archive can be accessed via password from a web user interface and service users with high and low volume connectivity. The Jagwire architecture enables providing NASA data to all users, worldwide—achieving the goals of open data access.

Jagwire was designed around seven tenets:

- Deploy next to the sensor and data sources when possible
- Leave the data where it was collected
- Move the data only when it is required
- Move the data only to where it is required
- Minimize the amount of data sent
- Send the answer and not the data when possible
- Anything within the enterprise can be a sensor and/or a consumer.

These tenets are designed to leverage data as close to NRT as possible. Satellite imagery arriving in the Jagwire systems requires agreements with commercial satellite providers and appropriate configurations with government provided data. HGSI can configure direct connectivity from data sources to Jagwire to include satellite datasets.

2 Open Science

Jagwire is a still imagery and video data management software solution used for capturing, ingesting, indexing, archiving, searching and disseminating the various forms of geospatial intelligence and its associated metadata. Jagwire can process a wide range of data formats including HDF5. All of the data formats ingested into Jagwire are made available to low bandwidth users to provide situational awareness (think accessing data doing field work) and to high bandwidth users for advanced exploitation. Data are federated across locations so holdings at one site appear as part of a whole.

At a high level, the following are a list of key features, functions and architectural highlights related to accessibility:

- Instant, intuitive and unified access to multiple data sources (Full Motion Video, Wide-Area Motion Imagery, Imagery, SAR and LIDAR Products).
- Enterprise-wide visibility with search, discover and stream capability.
- Searchability via drag and draw, tags and metadata.
- High performance on low-bandwidth and high latency networks.
- Standards-based and interoperable.
- Includes an Intuitive web-based user interface where analytics can be deployed.
- Flexible and scalable, from large data centres, to airborne assets, to mobile devices.

Figure 2, Data from collection modality to users

3 Component Technology

Jagwire includes components that enable transformative data access and efficiencies. Jagwire makes it easy to take data from archival systems, discover it, tag it, make available to various organizations and user levels, provides on the fly analytics and break down barriers to data use. See Table 1 below for additional details.

Table 1, Jagwire Components

Complete end-to-end geospatial content management, discovery and dissemination solution for near-real-time environments
Supports near-real time ingest and on the fly transcoding of multiple simultaneous full motion video feeds with low-latency over disadvantaged networks
Enables situational awareness via common operating picture
Thin client – intuitive web browser based UI for access anywhere, from the desktop, cloud or mobile
Quickly and easily search large, disparate data holdings with a variety of methods using metadata, keyword, geospatial, temporal and user defined tags

Supports common processed geospatial data formats – defence and commercial (FMV, imagery, SAR, LiDAR)
Highly scalable, from large-scale multi-server enterprise operations to small form factors at the tactical edge
Real-time unified search across federated nodes of all ingested assets across network connected systems
Supports remote management, remote system administration
Highly flexible, designed to easily integrate into existing COTS solutions
Supports installations on-prem or in the cloud
Highly secure, approved for classified environments and implements robust video security enhancements
Open Geospatial Consortium Support (OGC) – WMS, WFS, WCS

4 Downstream Interoperability

ENVI is the HGSI solution for image analysis requirements, outputs into many open data formats that are consumable by other applications and tightly integrated with ESRI products. ENVI can be linked to Jagwire to access Earth Science data available in Jagwire's archives, allowing users to create, publish and deploy advanced ENVI image and data analytics across the enterprise. ENVI can fuse multiple data modalities like RADAR, LiDAR, SAR, optical, hyperspectral, multispectral, stereo, thermal and acoustic to create composite datasets that exploit the strengths and weaknesses of each modality and incorporates automation tools to rapidly analyse large data sets. ENVI can be extended with modules for atmospheric correction, the digital elevation model generation, deep learning and extended with IDL—a widely used application at NASA. Applications developed with IDL can be deployed freely with the IDL Virtual Machine. ENVI can also call algorithms developed by Python to integrate the wide range of file support with the broad user community of Python. Figure 3 shows how Jagwire can take data from a collection modality (in this case the California Air National Guard) and make analytics products available then users.

Figure 3, Jagwire as part of an analytics and dissemination platform

Jagwire has the capability to utilise ENVI analytics to deliver automated processing and content extraction. For example, this includes object detection via deep-learning classifiers, material detection via spectral analysis and change detection via SAR processing. While ENVI, IDL and Jagwire are commercial offerings, HGSI provides flexible offerings to integrate with NASA Open Science and Open Data. HGSI's goal is to make it as easy as possible to extract information from virtually any remote sensing modality or scientific dataset and bring the value from that data to a large community.

5 Relevant Webpages

<https://www.l3harrisgeospatial.com/>

<https://www.l3harris.com/all-capabilities/goes-r-series-ground-segment-and-antenna-segment>